

Topic Modeling French Crime Fiction

Proposal for the Digital Humanities Conference 2015

Christof Schöch
University of Würzburg, Germany
christof.schoech@uni-wuerzburg.de

Introduction

This study applies topic modeling to a collection of French crime fiction novels with the aim of discovering topic-related patterns. The results show both expected and novel patterns related to authors, subgenres, and time period. Topic modeling proves a useful quantitative method for investigating the history of French crime fiction.

1. French Crime Fiction

Crime fiction can be defined as a type of narrative prose fiction whose plot revolves around the elucidation of a (usually) violent crime through a (more or less) rational investigation (often) taking place in an urban setting and (typically) involving (one or several) investigators, victims, witnesses, suspects and criminals. French crime fiction's rich history goes back to the 1860s and has many highly prolific proponents. Prototypical crime fiction novels are easily recognized, but the precise boundaries of the genre and as its internal divisions into subgenres remain a matter of debate (see Lits 1998, Colin 1999, Lavergne 2009, Todorov 1971). The abundant material is a challenge to any reader's time and memory but an opportunity for quantitative methods like topic modeling.

2. Research Questions

This study addresses the following questions: How prevalent are expected themes such as crime and investigation, and which other themes are important? What relations exist between topics and categories like authorship, subgenre, or time period? What kind of groupings of novels does one obtain based on topic similarity? What new insights into the history of crime fiction does topic modeling allow?

4. Method

Topic Modeling discovers latent semantic structure in large collections of texts. Technically, a topic is a probability distribution over word frequencies; in turn, each text is characterized by a distribution over topics. In practice, the words with the highest scores in a given topic are mostly semantically related words; the topics with the highest scores in a text are assumed to represent the text's major themes (see Steyvers & Griffiths 2007). Besides Latent Dirichlet Allocation (Blei 2003), there is now an increasing number of alternative algorithms, such as Non-Negative Matrix Factorization (Xu et al. 2003). Several implementations are available, like MALLET (McCallum 2002) or packages for R and Python, as well as tutorials (e.g.

Graham et al. 2012, Riddell 2014). Topic Modeling has proven immensely popular in Digital Humanities (e.g. Blevins 2010, Rhody 2012, Jockers 2013).

3. Data

For this study, a collection of 250 French novels published between 1858 and 2012 was created. The vast majority are crime fiction novels (in the widest sense), but for several authors, some non-crime fiction novels have also been included. The collection includes novels pertaining to several subgenres and written by 14 different authors (Ponson du Terrail, Du Boisgobey, Gaboriau, Leroux, Leblanc, Simenon, Malet, Dard, Japrisot, Manchette, Pouy, Vargas, Echenoz, Daeninckx) and has around 16 millions words. Texts in the public domain have been obtained online (mostly from ebooksgratuits.com), while additional texts have been scanned, submitted to OCR and manually corrected.

French being a highly inflected language, all words have been lemmatized. For the results reported here, nouns have exclusively been selected for analysis after tagging with TreeTagger (Schmidt 1994) and texts have been split into segments of 30 nouns each. MALLET has been run with 60 target topics.

5. Results & Discussion

5.1 Topics obtained

The topics obtained can manually be labeled by their dominant semantic trait (Fig. 1; see Annex for a complete list).

topic	score	label	top-ranked words
#00	0.047	family1	père an fils mère fille nom enfant famille frère année mariage
#08	0.039	letters	lettre papier enveloppe nom écriture mot billet poche main feuille adresse
#11	0.012	gambling	jeu carte partie joueur coup cercle table course point dé fois
#13	0.055	informal2	coup mec gars gros genre dame air même temps truc type
#14	0.072	interior	porte chambre escalier fenêtre étage bruit pièce maison clef couloir voix
#28	0.047	money	franc argent billet monsieur affaire somme million cent jour banque fortune
#42	0.061	crime2	coup cri main bras voix œil tête mort moment sang corps
#54	0.057	investigation1	police commissaire affaire agent crime assassin cadavre mort chef monsieur enquête

Figure 1: Selection from the 60 topics obtained with 10 top-ranked words.

The subjective topic coherence is very high: few top-ranked words do not share semantic traits, and few topics are hard to interpret (but see Chang et al. 2009; Schmidt 2012). Most topics could appear in many types of novels: general topics like #00 or #28 (“family” and “money”), or more specific ones like #08 or #11 (“letters” and “gambling”). Only seven out of sixty topics are clearly related to crime fiction, such as #42 and #54 (labeled “crime2” and “detection”). Judged by its topic composition alone, crime fiction appears to be a less distinctive sub-genre of the novel than expected. Note that topics can be based on various types of similarity: topic #14 (“interiors”) is related to a recurrent setting, topic #13 (“informal2”) to a specific register. Some semantic fields (“family”, “crime”, “detection”) appear in several topics and share top-ranked words.

5.2 Authorship, subgenre and time

Topic scores per text segment can be aggregated, for instance, to the document, author, genre, or time period levels.

topic	label	Dard	Pouy	Malet	Sim.	Echen.	Manch.	Japris.	Leblanc	Daen.	Ponson	Boisgo.	Vargas	Gabor.	Leroux	stdev
#19	informal3	0.013	0.034	0.010	0.008	0.014	0.015	0.012	0.006	0.016	0.004	0.005	0.224	0.004	0.006	0.0573
#53	informal1	0.038	0.050	0.210	0.012	0.014	0.037	0.015	0.009	0.027	0.005	0.007	0.020	0.006	0.007	0.0530
#13	informal2	0.197	0.059	0.020	0.006	0.013	0.026	0.011	0.005	0.015	0.004	0.005	0.012	0.005	0.006	0.0508
#07	bourgeoisie3	0.016	0.010	0.018	0.016	0.010	0.011	0.012	0.033	0.010	0.034	0.039	0.012	0.175	0.030	0.0429
#51	civil-service	0.018	0.114	0.017	0.012	0.039	0.045	0.008	0.008	0.134	0.005	0.006	0.023	0.007	0.008	0.0410
#49	bourgeoisie1	0.009	0.005	0.011	0.009	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.014	0.006	0.019	0.145	0.007	0.021	0.017	0.0365
#23	aviation	0.016	0.021	0.009	0.005	0.113	0.023	0.010	0.005	0.033	0.002	0.002	0.015	0.002	0.005	0.0286
#26	automobile	0.034	0.055	0.025	0.018	0.047	0.066	0.077	0.013	0.066	0.004	0.005	0.022	0.004	0.007	0.0258
#21	investigation2	0.026	0.012	0.033	0.103	0.021	0.030	0.045	0.025	0.034	0.006	0.008	0.026	0.008	0.009	0.0248
#48	(unclear)	0.029	0.023	0.036	0.025	0.035	0.019	0.016	0.112	0.023	0.021	0.043	0.031	0.037	0.040	0.0236
#02	time-of-year	0.016	0.024	0.016	0.082	0.026	0.019	0.072	0.014	0.025	0.011	0.013	0.021	0.015	0.011	0.0223
#29	body-parts	0.026	0.036	0.021	0.013	0.024	0.094	0.031	0.012	0.030	0.008	0.008	0.033	0.009	0.015	0.0220
#32	bathroom	0.016	0.011	0.014	0.026	0.021	0.036	0.082	0.006	0.016	0.005	0.004	0.015	0.005	0.007	0.0203
#30	verybritish	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.004	0.001	0.069	0.002	0.002	0.004	0.002	0.0179
#18	nobility	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.004	0.005	0.002	0.008	0.003	0.070	0.009	0.003	0.016	0.005	0.0178

Figure 2: Distribution of topic scores at the author level

(15 topics with the largest variation, measured in standard deviations, across authors)

On the author level (Fig. 2), it appears that several (but not all) authors have a distinctive “signature topic”: a topic with a particularly high score in comparison both to other topics for the same author and to the same topic for other authors. For example, Gaboriau’s signature topic is #07 (“bourgeoisie1”), with a score of 0.175. The closest topic for Gaboriau is #03 (only 0.053), while the closest author for the same topic is Boisgobey (only 0.039). Simenon’s signature topic, “investigation2”, is more genre-specific but also less distinctive of this author. For some authors (Japrisot, Leroux), no clear signature topic emerges.

Compared to authors, most subgenres have less marked characteristic topics (Fig. 3).

topic	label	archaïque	judiciaire	détection	noir	néopolar	parodique	thriller	blanche	stdev
#13	informal2	0.006	0.004	0.005	0.046	0.026	0.244	0.009	0.033	0.0812
#23	aviation	0.005	0.002	0.003	0.017	0.020	0.023	0.139	0.024	0.0455
#07	bourgeoisie3	0.031	0.078	0.101	0.014	0.011	0.016	0.010	0.031	0.0343
#53	informal1	0.008	0.006	0.010	0.093	0.030	0.029	0.012	0.037	0.0285
#51	civil-service	0.008	0.005	0.010	0.032	0.087	0.024	0.023	0.027	0.0260
#52	funeral	0.014	0.007	0.006	0.006	0.005	0.008	0.007	0.069	0.0218
#55	navigation	0.018	0.006	0.007	0.012	0.016	0.013	0.071	0.023	0.0211
#19	informal3	0.006	0.004	0.006	0.067	0.018	0.014	0.009	0.021	0.0208
#21	investigation2	0.016	0.007	0.071	0.032	0.029	0.021	0.014	0.010	0.0204
#48	(unclear)	0.069	0.029	0.035	0.031	0.020	0.028	0.068	0.015	0.0204
#26	automobile	0.010	0.004	0.011	0.035	0.064	0.032	0.024	0.026	0.0189
#49	bourgeoisie1	0.016	0.050	0.014	0.009	0.005	0.009	0.004	0.016	0.0146
#25	theater	0.008	0.008	0.006	0.011	0.014	0.012	0.010	0.050	0.0144
#03	judiciary	0.024	0.029	0.038	0.007	0.006	0.007	0.005	0.034	0.0139
#18	nobility	0.006	0.043	0.010	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.002	0.012	0.0137

Figure 3: Topic scores aggregated to the subgenre level

(15 topics with the largest variation, measured in standard deviations, across genres)

For example, the classical detective novel’s most characteristic topic is #07 with a score of 0.101. The closest topic for the same subgenre is #21 (still 0.071), while the closest subgenre for the same topic is “roman criminel” (still 0.078). However, the traditional genre labels used here are problematic, because most of them refer to periods rather than structural types and correlate strongly with time period and authorship.

The distribution of topics at the level of time period lets interesting patterns emerge (Fig. 4). As expected, some topics gain while others lose in importance over time. Some very similar topics “take turns”, as it were, with successive peaks (“bourgeoisie”, top right, and “informal”, bottom left).

Figure 4: Topic scores per decade for four topic groups.

Each peak is associated with one author and their period of activity: for “bourgeoisie”, Boisgobey and Gaboriau; for “informal”, Malet, Dard, and Vargas (see Fig. 2). The latter topic’s rapid rise in the 1940s underlines how bold Malet’s use of informal language was, but also shows the (problematic) impact of individual authors on these temporal patterns.

Beyond individual topic development, the rate of change in topics scores from one decade to the next gives an insight into the innovation cycles of crime fiction (Fig. 5).

Figure 5: Cumulated absolute differences between topic scores from one decade to the next

Values above the 2-degree polynomial trendline indicate periods of intense topic-related innovation and, possibly, generational shifts (notably: 1880s-1900s and 1930s-1940s). Values below indicate periods of relative continuity (notably: 1910s-1920s and 1940s-1960s). Such results provide a fresh perspective on periodization in literary history.

4.3 Author similarity

Based on the topic scores per novel, author or genre, Principal Component Analysis (see Jolliffe 2002) yields groupings of topically similar items, independently of preexisting classifications.

The PCA plots in Fig. 6 are based on topic scores aggregated to the author level and have been obtained using the „stylo“ package for R (Eder et al. 2013). The first two components retain large parts of the variation in the data (31.3% and 12.6% respectively).

Figure 6: PCA plot of aggregated topic scores per author: authors (right) and loadings (left)

Not surprisingly for a collection of texts spanning 150 years, the first component is correlated with time period: in the plot, authors active before 1930 are located to the east, those active from 1930-1960 close to the middle, and those active after 1960 to the west. A notable exception is Fred Vargas: although writing in the late twentieth century, she appears close to Malet and Dard: the topic-based grouping reveals a link between the now-classic “roman noir” and its later reinterpretation by Vargas. Note that although the three authors each have an “informal” topic as their “signature topic” (see above), their proximity remains unchanged even when these topics are removed. Japrisot’s unique work rightly stands out, but his relative proximity to Simenon remains to be explained.

Conclusions and Future Work

The results obtained here shed a new light on the history of French crime fiction. Authors, subgenres and time periods each have distinctive topic characteristics. Some well-understood facts about the genre can be confirmed, but new insights into the genre’s thematic history also become possible. Topic modeling proves to be a valuable tool, providing a fresh perspective on literary history and prompting new interrogations about periodization and the contours of subgenres.

Future work will involve two areas: The text collection will be expanded with a view to reduce correlation between authors, subgenres and time period. Also, the precise relation between topics and certain categories (e.g. subgenres) will be further investigated using supervised topic modeling (see McAuliffe & Blei 2008, Ramage et al. 2009).

References

- Blei, D. M., Griffiths, T., Jordan, M. I., & Tenenbaum, J. B. (2004). "Hierarchical Topic Models and the Nested Chinese Restaurant Process". In S. Thrun, L. K. Saul, & B. Schölkopf (Eds.), *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 16*. MIT Press.
- Blei, D. M., Ng, A. Y., & Jordan, M. I. (2003). "Latent dirichlet allocation". *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 3, 993–1022.
- Blevins, C. (2010, April). "Topic Modeling Martha Ballard's Diary".
<http://history.org/2010/04/01/topic-modeling-martha-ballards-diary/>
- Chang, J., Boyd-Graber, J. L., Gerrish, S., Wang, C., & Blei, D. M. (2009). "Reading Tea Leaves: How Humans Interpret Topic Models". In *Neural Information Processing Systems*, 288–296.
- Colin, J.-P. (1999). *La belle époque du roman policier français. Aux origines d'un genre romanesque*. Lausanne: Delachaux et Niestlé.
- Eder, M., Kestemont, M., & Rybicki, J. (2013). "Stylometry with R: a suite of tools". In *Digital Humanities 2013: Conference Abstracts*, 487–489. Lincoln: University of Nebraska.
- Jockers, M. L. (2013). *Macroanalysis: Digital Methods and Literary History*. University of Illinois Press.
- Jolliffe, I. T. (2002). *Principal Component Analysis* (2nd edition.). Springer.
- Lavergne, E. (2009). *La naissance du roman policier français*. Paris: Garnier.
- Lits, M. (1993). *Le roman policier. Introduction à la théorie et l'histoire d'un genre littéraire*. Liège: Éd. du CÉFAL.
- McCauley, J. D., & Blei, D. M. (2008). "Supervised Topic Models". In J. C. Platt, D. Koller, Y. Singer, & S. T. Roweis (Eds.), *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 20*, 121–128.
<http://papers.nips.cc/paper/3328-supervised-topic-models.pdf>
- McCallum, A. K. (2002). *MALLET: A Machine Learning for Language Toolkit*.
<http://mallet.cs.umass.edu>
- Mesplède, C. (Ed.). (2007). *Dictionnaire des littératures policières*. Paris: Joseph K.
- Ramage, D., Hall, D., Nallapati, R., & Manning, C. D. (2009). "Labeled LDA: A Supervised Topic Model for Credit Attribution in Multi-labeled Corpora". In *Proceedings of the 2009 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing: Volume 1 - Volume 1*, 248–256.
- Rhody, L. M. (2012). "Topic Modeling and Figurative Language". *Journal of Digital Humanities*, 2(1). <http://journalofdigitalhumanities.org/2-1/topic-modeling-and-figurative-language-by-lisa-m-rhody/>
- Riddell, A. B. (2014). "Text Analysis with Topic Models for the Humanities and Social Sciences (TAToM)". DARIAH-DE. <https://de.dariah.eu/tatom/>.
- Rubin, T. N., Chambers, A., Smyth, P., & Steyvers, M. (2012). "Statistical topic models for multi-label document classification". *Machine Learning*, 88(1-2), 157–208. doi:10.1007/s10994-011-5272-5
- Schmid, H. (1994). "Probabilistic Part-of-Speech Tagging Using Decision Trees". In *Proceedings of International Conference on New Methods in Language Processing*.
- Schmidt, B. M. (2011). "Words Alone: Dismantling Topic Models in the Humanities". *Journal of Digital Humanities* 2(1). <http://journalofdigitalhumanities.org/2-1/words-alone-by-benjamin-m-schmidt/>
- Steyvers, M., & Griffiths, T. (2006). "Probabilistic Topic Models". In T. Landauer, D. McNamara, S. Dennis, & W. Kintsch (Eds.), *Latent Semantic Analysis: A Road to Meaning*. Laurence Erlbaum.
- Todorov, T. (1971). "Typologie du roman policier". In *Poétique de la prose*, 55–65. Paris: Seuil.
- Xu, W., Liu, X., & Gong, Y. (2003). "Document Clustering Based on Non-negative Matrix Factorization". In *Proceedings of the 26th Annual International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Informaion Retrieval*, 267–273. doi:10.1145/860435.860485

Annex: List of 60 topics with their overall score, label and 10 top-ranked words

topic	score	label	top-ranked words
#00	0.04687	family1	père an fils mère fille nom enfant famille frère année mariage
#01	0.01229	reading	livre page roman peste texte bouquin bibliothèque auteur ouvrage titre histoire
#02	0.05432	time-of-year	jour an fois mois soir temps semaine maison matin heure année
#03	0.04309	judiciary	monsieur juge instruction justice avocat père crime magistrat affaire président maître
#04	0.02062	nobility2	prince empereur princesse maître père grand-duc voix impératrice ami monseigneur palais
#05	0.03873	countryside	route bois chemin arbre forêt terre chien village pied château nuit
#06	0.03006	military	soldat candeur officier guerre colonel troupe armée coup chef ordre capitaine
#07	0.09282	bourgeoisie3	monsieur mademoiselle madame fille père ami comte voix moment œil mot
#08	0.03863	letters	lettre papier enveloppe nom écriture mot billet poche main feuille adresse
#09	0.03828	drinking	verre table bouteille café vin heure bar comptoir bière œil main
#10	0.03426	interior	pièce mur table chambre meuble fauteuil salon porte salle tableau cheminée
#11	0.01208	gambling	jeu carte partie joueur coup cercle table course point dé fois
#12	0.06683	life-death-love	vie mort jour pensée amour cœur heure fois âme idée œil
#13	0.05494	informal2	coup mec gars gros genre dame air même temps truc type
#14	0.07177	interior	porte chambre escalier fenêtre étage bruit pièce maison clef couloir voix
#15	0.02177	train	train gare quai wagon station voyageur compartiment voie valise heure voiture
#16	0.02275	smoking	cigarette poche boîte paquet main pipe papier cigare tabac sac allumette
#17	0.01822	royalty	roi madame cour jour reine comte amour maîtresse dame amant duc
#18	0.03118	nobility	monsieur marquis vicomte baron duc don heure lettre valet nom jour
#19	0.04219	informal3	type chien tête flic commissaire main gars an heure lieutenant vieux
#20	0.02070	family2	enfant mère maman fils père fille dame madame papa bras maison
#21	0.05625	investigation2	bureau heure commissaire téléphone inspecteur rue voix numéro police patron temps
#22	0.01800	navigation2	capitaine bord mer navire matelot port bateau eau côte pont île
#23	0.02857	aviation	appareil temps machine fil écran air film avion point musique fond
#24	0.03869	nighttime	nuit lumière soleil ombre ciel fenêtre vent jour rayon œil temps
#25	0.02459	theater	scène salle musique théâtre foule loge orchestre air place monde soir
#26	0.04782	automobile	voiture route auto rue volant côté mètre portière chauffeur véhicule moteur
#27	0.01658	(unclear)	bossu officier lieutenant ami affaire citoyen temps hercule commandant soldat camarade
#28	0.04671	money	franc argent billet monsieur affaire somme million cent jour banque fortune
#29	0.04733	body-parts	main tête sang bras pied coup œil corps jambe doigt épaule
#30	0.02145	verybritish	miss sir lord enfant irlandais mistress abbé milady gentleman major révérend
#31	0.03960	face	œil cheveu visage an regard nez air lèvres tête barbe figure
#32	0.03088	bathroom	chambre lit bain porte salle nuit eau main robe œil tête
#33	0.02300	crime1	arme coup revolver balle main fusil pistolet feu canon poche crosse
#34	0.02800	medical	docteur médecin jour lit infirmier hôpital état chambre blessure malade heure
#35	0.07481	time-of-day	heure matin soir nuit jour chambre temps lendemain fois quart journée
#36	0.02692	nobility2	comte monsieur madame sir baccarat vicomte heure hôtel valet main chambre
#37	0.02688	underground	trou mur cave pied main corde porte coup pierre fer sol
#38	0.02715	journalism	journal photo article journaux page journaliste presse nom titre papier numéro
#39	0.01512	jewelery	clef bijou main or diamant coffre objet poche coffret clé perle
#40	0.07523	(unclear)	fois question tête peur temps air monde idée mot histoire gens
#41	0.03975	clothes	chapeau pantalon chemise robe main cheveu vêtement veste pied œil cravate
#42	0.06110	crime2	coup cri main bras voix œil tête mort moment sang corps
#43	0.02846	eating	table vin pain cuisine assiette repas faim verre morceau café plat
#44	0.02119	horse-carriage	cheval voiture monsieur cocher route heure maître poste pied écurie valet
#45	0.01557	prison	prison gardien prisonnier cellule porte jour heure baigne bourreau forçat gouverneur
#46	0.03965	exterior	jardin maison fenêtre mur arbre grille cour pavillon toit côté étage
#47	0.08601	face	main œil voix tête regard visage bras lèvres geste mot épaule
#48	0.09798	(unclear)	fait jour affaire moment point raison fois un événement plan idée
#49	0.04813	bourgeoisie1	madame monsieur marquise ami mari dame capitaine nom oncle mademoiselle personne
#50	0.05446	urbanity	rue maison voiture porte boulevard heure place hôtel quartier trottoir coin
#51	0.05144	civil-service	année groupe service an inspecteur nom travail mois monde temps cours
#52	0.02033	funeral	église cimetière mort prêtre curé cercueil tombe croix abbé terre pierre
#53	0.06645	informal1	type flic coup nom genre temps gars copain affaire question air
#54	0.05653	investigation1	police commissaire affaire agent crime assassin cadavre mort chef monsieur enquête
#55	0.02904	navigation	eau mer pont bord île barque fleuve sable rivière mètre bateau
#56	0.0444	bourgeoisie2	monsieur ami madame mademoiselle directeur messieurs porte affaire secrétaire moment tête
#57	0.05926	family2	fille enfant main dieu père mère cœur œil larme jour amour
#58	0.01426	science	professeur oncle travail science laboratoire esprit poupée monde invention expérience perroquet
#59	0.06339	(unclear)	vie ami monde an jour fille gens temps idée plaisir année